

CULTIVATION OF LENTILS IN CONDITIONS OF THE SOUTHERN
REGIONS OF UZBEKISTAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7021324>

Abstract

The lentil plant is grown for food purposes; it is superior to leguminous crops due to its quick-dissolving protein content, high palatability, and ease of digestion. Cereals and flour are used in the preparation of various cuisines.

Key words: lentil, plant, variety, line, pods, seeds.

Lentils are also used as fodder crops. For feed, its grain, straw, waste - pulp is used. Lentils, like other leguminous crops, enrich the soil with nitrogen and are considered a good successor crop. Lentils contain 21.3-36.0 percent protein, 0.7-1.4 percent fat, 2.5-3.6 percent ash, 43.8-53.9 percent starch, 2.7-4.5 percent cell phone is available.

According to Academician N.I. Vavilov, the center of primary origin of lentil crop is South-West Asia. Its large-seeded forms emerged later as a result of hybridization, selection, and favorable Mediterranean conditions. The Mediterranean Sea is the primary origin of large-seeded lentils. Lentils are very old cultivated plants. Lentil is considered a cultural plant of the East, and it has been cultivated as a crop since ancient times in India, Greece, and Egypt.

Biological properties of lentils. Common lentil - *Lens esculenta* Moench (synonym: *Lens culmenars* Mdc,vm *lens* L) is an annual plant with a height of 25-50 cm. Its stem is thin, 4-sided, mostly upright, sometimes prostrate, finely hairy, reddish in color, and the root is an arrowroot with little branching. The leaves are complex, double-winged, lower 2-3, upper 4-8 pairs. The leaves are oval in shape [1, 2].

Lentil is a self-pollinating plant, but hybrids are also found in natural conditions. This condition can be observed mainly during periods of drought. The calyx consists of 5 butterfly-shaped petals: an axillary, 2 wings arising from 2 petals and a boat. Changchilari 10 pieces, one free, mother from the beginning to the end in the form of a leaf, bent and hairy. The muzzle is small [3, 4].

The growth cycle of the lentil crop can be divided into 4 stages: seed germination and germination, tillering, flowering and ripening. The period of development of lentils, like most legumes, is divided into 3 stages: 1- from planting to germination, 2- from emergence to flowering, 3- from flowering to ripening. The duration of these developmental stages varies mainly depending on the external environment. Their speed mainly depends on the coefficient of useful heat, which varies depending on the duration of planting.

Preparation for growing lentils in dry areas begins in the winter months with the clearing of the remnants of previous and wild plants. The area where the product is grown and the field waste are cleared of previous and wild plant residues and are collected and burned. When these prophylactic works are carried out on time, the overwintering mushrooms of insects are reduced by 10-11%, and the seeds of weeds are reduced by 20-22%. Due to limited irrigation possibilities in hilly areas, winter plowing is carried out to accumulate moisture reserves. Before winter plowing, 100 percent of the annual rate of mineral fertilizers (in the amount of 80-100 kg/ha of nitrogen, 90 kg of phosphorus and 60 kg of potassium-acting substance) is sprinkled with phosphorus and potassium fertilizers using the NRU-05 mechanism and plowed at a depth of 25-30 cm.

Before planting, it is necessary to level the field to make it high-quality. The formation of depressions in the lentil field where rainwater collects causes the plants to suffer from diseases and wither. It is recommended to plant winter lentils until the second decade of November.

The seeds can be sown in several different ways, using pneumatic seed drills on leveled fields or ditches. In pneumatic seeders, the seeds are sown in a row in 60 cm wide rows. When the planting pattern is 60x2-3 cm, 833,300 seedlings are left on each hectare. Sowing rate is 55-90 kg/ha for small-seeded and large-seeded varieties respectively. 70-120 kg/ha of seed is used for sowing by hand.

The use of high-yielding and high-quality seeds for planting winter lentil seeds, as well as treating the seeds against fungal diseases and insects before planting, are one of the main factors for obtaining a high yield.

The growth and development of winter lentil sprouts is slow in the initial stages. Its development accelerates as it transitions from weeding to weeding. In early spring, in order to soften the soil, heat it, keep it moist and clean it from weeds, it is necessary to work between the rows of crops with a cultivator KRX-4. In this case, the working organs of the cultivator KRX-4 should be placed at

least 10-12 cm deep, and 8-10 cm away from the plant. As a result of cultivation between the rows, the surface of the soil is softened and broken, air exchange of the soil is improved, weed lawns are destroyed.

During the growing period of winter lentils, the rows are softened 2-3 times, and the plants should be hoed 2-3 times by hand to remove the weeds around them. Inter-row tillage can be stopped only when it is not possible to insert equipment between the plant rows.

In early spring, the first feeding of winter lentils with nitrogen fertilizers is carried out during the grassing stage of the plants. It is required to give 30-40% of the annual rate of nitrogen fertilizer. When feeding plants with nitrogen fertilizer for the second time, the remainder of the annual norm is applied to a depth of at least 14-18 cm with a cultivator during the flowering stage.

Winter lentils are resistant to diseases and pests. Depending on the development of the plant, the suspension is given twice during the growing season. The suspension satisfies the plant's need for water for 10-15 days along with additional nutrition. The lentil fields are controlled every two days with the help of pheromone traps for the spread of diseases and insects. If 3 or more butterflies have fallen on the pheromone traps, the specified order and quantity of bracon, trichogram and golden eye are placed on each hectare.

75-85% ripened winter lentil plants are harvested by hand, collected in a row for 1-2 days, and then the grains are separated in a combine harvester. The harvest from the combine is cleaned of plant residues and dead seeds, the grain is dried to 14.0-15.0 percent moisture, packed in 25 or 50 kg bags and placed in storage warehouses.

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